

THE INFLUENCE OF COVERING RATE OF SOYBEAN SEEDS WITH BENTONITE CLAY ON GERMINATION DYNAMICS

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Abstract. The article presents the scientific basis of saving irrigation water by treating soybeans with bentonite clay. With its help, the influence of soybean on the germination dynamics of "Arleta" and "Nafis" varieties was studied in light gray soils of Kashkadarya region.

Key words: bentonite slurry, agricultural ore, bark, germination dynamics.

ВЛИЯНИЕ СТЕПЕНИ ПОКРЫТИЯ СЕМЯН СОИ БЕНТОНИТОВОЙ ГЛИНОЙ НА ДИНАМИКУ ПРОРАСТАНИЯ

Аннотация. В статье представлены научные основы экономии поливной воды путем обработки сои бентонитовой глиной. По ней изучено влияние сои на динамику всхожести сортов «Арлета» и «Нафис» на светло-серых почвах Кашкадарьинской области.

Ключевые слова: бентонитовый илам, агроруда, шелушение, динамика прорастания.

The role and importance of the agricultural sector in ensuring food security for the population of our republic is increasing day by day. One of the most important tasks is to use the available resources and opportunities in our country to ensure the guaranteed supply of agricultural products to the population, to further increase productivity and interest, and to process agricultural products.

In paragraph 3.3 of the Strategy of Actions for 2017-2021 on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is stated "...consistent development of agricultural production, further strengthening of the country's food security, production of environmentally friendly products important tasks such as expanding production, significantly increasing the export potential of the agrarian sector, reducing the areas of cotton and grain crops, planting potatoes, vegetables, feed and oil crops on vacant lands.

In the world's leading countries, norms for the use of non-traditional agro-ores in various soil conditions as additional nutrients to mineral fertilizers have been developed and scientifically based. As a result of the application of non-traditional agro-minerals to the soil as a resource-saving technology, the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of the soil are improved, the biological processes in the soil are accelerated, the coefficient of absorption of the applied mineral fertilizers by plants increases, and as a result, the productivity increases. together with the improvement of quality.

The world experience of using non-traditional agro-ores shows that their use provides 10-15% higher yield from agricultural crops, improves the quality of the product, and agro-ores cleans the soil from heavy metals, toxic substances and radioactive elements. . In this regard, bentonite mud fills the soil's demand for microelements and improves its reclamation condition. Bentonite mud retains moisture in the soil, collects sand particles around it, and increases the viscosity of the sand. Bentonite mud is considered a source of food for plants, it contains 0.3-4.7% carbon, 0.4-

3.0% potassium, 0.3-1.5% phosphorus elements, trace elements copper, zinc, boron, cobalt, molybdenum, manganese, sulfur are existing.

Based on the above, our research within the framework of the practical project PZ-202102154 "Development of science-based agrotechnologies of irrigation water conservation using bentonite clay in the cultivation of agricultural crops" under the conditions of light gray soils of Kashkadarya region of soybean "Arleta" and "Nafis" varieties at the rate of 400,000 pieces/ha, the seeds were coated with bentonite clay and planted at a depth of 3-4 cm, and its effect on germination dynamics was determined.

In this experiment, the dynamics of soybean seed germination was not affected by irrigation regimes. However, depending on the rate of coating of soybean seeds with bentonite clay, the effect on the dynamics of germination was clearly felt.

That is, compared to soybean varieties ChDNS, the rate of mineral fertilizers in the 60-70-70, 70-75-75 and 75-80-80% irrigation regimes is the control (untreated) variant and the seed 30 with bentonite clay; 22.3-40.3 in "Arleta" variety when observations were made on April 15, depending on the dynamics of seed germination, irrigation method and bentonite clay in 40 and 50 kg/t shelled variants; 24.5-41.0 and 24.9-41.6%, 46.3-75.5 when the observations were made on April 17; 48.3-76.3 and 49.0-77.4%, 71.8-93.0 on April 19; Fertility was 74.3-91.5 and 75.4-92.9%, and according to the indicators, in soybean variety "Nafis" on April 15, it was 24.0-41.8; 24.5-43.0 and 24.9-43.6%, 41.3-74.5 when the observations were made on April 17; 46.0-76.5 and 46.7-77.6%, and on April 19, 74.5-94.5; It changed to 77.0-97.3 and 78.2-98.7% (Table 1).

In the experiment, the seeds of soybean varieties were compared to the control (untreated) version with bentonite clay 30; 8.5-9.3, depending on the standards of 40 and 50 kg/t shelled; By 16.5-17.5 and 19.8-20.3%, it significantly affected the dynamics of germination and accelerated germination.

Table-1

Influence of soybean seed coating with bentonite clay on germination dynamics

№ Var	Sorts	Irrigation procedure, (%)	Method of coating seeds with bentonite clay	Germination dynamics					
				Apr 15		Apr 17		Apr 19	
				piece	%	piece	%	piece	%
1	«Arleta»	ChDNS's (60-70-70 %)	Control (unprocessed)	89	22,3	185	46,3	287	71,8
2			30 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	124	31,0	243	60,8	321	80,3
3			40 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	146	36,5	297	74,3	353	88,3

4	«Nafis»	ChDNS's (70-75-75 %)	50 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	161	40,3	302	5,5	372	93,0
5			Control (unprocessed)	8	4,5	193	8,3	297	74,3
6			30 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	37	4,3	263	5,8	38	82,0
7			40 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	50	7,5	302	5,5	359	89,8
8			50 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	64	41,0	305	6,3	366	91,5
9		ChDNS's (75-80-80 %)	Control (unprocessed)	99	24,9	196	9,0	301	75,4
10			30 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	39	34,8	267	66,7	333	83,2
11			40 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	52	38,1	307	76,6	364	91,1
12			50 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	166	41,6	310	77,4	371	92,9
13		ChDNS's (60-70-70 %)	Control (unprocessed)	96	24,0	165	41,3	298	74,5
14			30 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	122	30,5	213	53,3	336	84,0
15			40 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	154	38,5	276	69,0	365	91,3
16			50 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	167	41,8	298	74,5	378	94,5
17		ChDNS's (70-75-75 %)	Control (unprocessed)	98	24,5	184	46,0	308	77,0
18			30 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	129	32,3	228	57,0	345	86,3

19		40 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	157	39,3	286	71,5	378	94,5
20		50 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	172	43,0	306	76,5	389	97,3
21	ChDNS's (75-80-80 %)	Control (unprocessed)	99	24,9	187	46,7	313	78,2
22		30 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	131	32,7	231	57,9	350	87,5
23		40 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	159	39,8	290	72,6	384	95,9
24		50 kg/t bentonite (seed coating)	175	43,6	311	77,6	395	98,7

It was found that the germination of soybean seeds coated with bentonite clay was observed in 6 days, and in the control version, which did not treat the seeds, it lasted up to 12 days. The reason for this was explained by the fact that the seeds coated with bentonite clay absorb moisture quickly and in large quantities.

Based on the information presented above, it can be concluded that as a result of treatment of soybean seeds with bentonite clay, the absorption of moisture by the seeds increases and the germination of uniform seeds is accelerated.

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